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TECHNOLOGY****INFLUENCE OF SCHOOL HEADS' INSTRUCTIONAL COMPETENCIES ON
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ABSTRACT

The study primarily aimed to determine the influence of school heads' instructional competencies on the teachers' management behavior in Leyte division, Philippines.

The descriptive-correlational design was adopted with the use of survey questionnaire as the tool in data gathering.

The teacher's performance for the last three years was very satisfactory. The level of instructional competence of the school heads fell on the competent category. In professional competency, the school heads evaluated their teachers very competently. The school heads showed the competence in motivating their teachers.

The management behavior of the school heads was highly effective. In the areas key processes and core components, the school heads were highly effective.

The instructional competencies of the school heads did not relate or affect their management behavior.

KEYWORDS: influence, school heads, instructional competencies, teachers, management behavior.

INTRODUCTION

Instructional supervision includes various roles and responsibilities that entail technical, professional and interpersonal aspects (Weller and Weller, 2002). It also includes strategies and actions to improve conditions for the teaching and learning process (Daresh et al., 2000). For schools to be effective, they need to look for opportunities to increase the professional development and job performance of teachers for the betterment in managing the teaching and learning process, and this can be done through supervision (Arong and Ogbadu, 2010). Hence, when taking on the responsibilities of a supervisor, the Head of Departments play an important role in promoting and developing the learning and professional growth of teachers. Head of Departments can be a major source of reliance and support for teachers when it comes to addressing issues and problems related to the teaching and learning process and instructional development. As such, it would be fitting to look into how the role of the Head of Departments as an instructional leader related to instructional supervision, will help teachers perform their jobs better.

Leaders who can provide the necessary leadership when managing the teachers' performance can have a large impact on their school's work environment and if the impact is positive, it may lead to teachers practicing and displaying desired behaviors in the workplace, especially in their commitment towards the school organizations (Hallinger and Heck, 1996a; Ponnusamy, 2010). Weber (1996) proved this in a study when he explained to increase teachers' commitment towards the schools; leaders need set high expectation on teachers' performance. Hence, for teachers to become more committed to the school, school leaders need to practice effective leadership behavior.

Principals have been found to affect the type of instruction teachers' use in their classrooms through their actions as instructional leaders (Blase & Blase, 1998; Blase & Roberts, 1994; King, 1991; Sheppard, 1996; Smith & Andrews, 1989).

The position of principal was chosen for investigation because it has been identified as an important component of an effective school (Cotton, 2003; Goodwin, Cunningham, & Childress, 2003; Hallinger & Heck, 1996). The U.S. Department of Education (2000) released a report portraying the principal's importance by listing ineffective principals as one of the barriers to improving teaching.

On the other hand, change in teachers' instructional practices refers to the amount of change in teachers' instructional practices over the previous two school years, 2006-2007 and 2007-2008. Changes in teachers' instructional practices were conceptualized as decreasing over the past two school years, increasing over the past two school years, remaining the same over the past two school years, or teachers did not use the practice during the last two school years.

The importance of teachers' instructional practices is demonstrated by current studies devoted to analyzing the effect of teacher quality on student achievement. Teacher quality refers to the characteristics and qualifications held by teachers (Stronge, 2002).

Kaplan and Owings (2002a) stated, "Staffing schools with highly qualified teachers who have strong teaching skills has become a national concern" (p. 22). They asserted that principals are responsible for hiring these individuals, further highlighting the need to examine how principals influence teachers.

Elmore (1999) asserted that principals are expected to possess the skills and knowledge to improve teacher instruction and student achievement. According to Lashway (2003) and Tucker (2003), the standards and accountability movement has increased the importance of the principal's role in school effectiveness.

More than ever before, principals are considered essential to the success of schools (Cotton, 2003; Goodwin et al., 2003). Principals are expected to be strong instructional leaders (Tucker, 2003; Wahlstrom & Louis, 2008). Knowing how principals influence the classroom instruction of teachers could aid principals in dealing with the rigorous demands set forth by the NCLB Act and state accountability systems.

The challenges of instructional leadership are rooted in the principal-agent problem. Galal (2002) defines the principal-agent problem as being at the core of any education reform. The principal (e.g., a ministry official, school principal) is interested in particular outcomes (such as good quality education), but has to rely on an agent (e.g., teachers) to obtain these outcomes. Chapman (2008) states that the focus on the principal agent problem places more concern with influencing the educational process in classrooms, where the real activities of learning occur. Lockheed and Verspoor (1991) observe that many of the teaching practices in developing countries are not conducive to student learning. Teaching practices often involve instruction for the whole class that emphasizes lectures by the teacher who then has students copy from the blackboard while offering them few opportunities to ask questions or participate in learning (Fuller and Heyneman, 1989). Classroom teaching in developing countries is also characterized by student memorization of texts with few opportunities to work actively with the material, and little ongoing monitoring and assessment of student learning through homework, classroom quizzes, or tests. The principal as instructional leader is charged to implement innovative teaching methods that engage students in more active rather than passive learning.

The purpose of this study is to measure how school principals influence change in teachers' management behavior; however, other factors influencing classroom instruction surfaced. The case of Leyte division is not yet determined since there are no studies conducted on this aspect. The researcher hopes to influence what principals are doing as instructional leaders and add to the understanding of what it means to be a leader of instruction particularly in her division. Information collected in this study could be useful in planning staff development opportunities for principals and in re-conceptualizing the content of principal preparation programs in Leyte division.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study aimed to address the main objective of finding out the influence of School heads' instructional competencies on teachers' management in Leyte division.

Specifically, this intended to answer the following:

1. Find out the socio-demographic profile of the respondents:
 - 1.1 School Principals

- 1.1.1. gender;
- 1.1.2 age;
- 1.1.3 civil status;
- 1.1.4 highest educational attainment; and
- 1.1.5 years of experience as school principal
- 1.2 Teachers
 - 1.2.1 gender;
 - 1.2.2 age;
 - 1.2.3 civil status;
 - 1.2.4 highest educational attainment; and
 - 1.2.5 number of years in teaching;
- 1.3 Performance
2. Find out the level of instructional competencies of the school heads;
3. Determine the management behavior of the school heads;
4. Determine the significant relationship between:
 - 4.1 Profile and Instructional Competencies;
 - 4.2 Profile and Management Behavior; and
 - 4.3 Instructional Competencies and Management Behavior

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between the profile and instructional competencies of the school heads;
H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between the profile and management behavior of the school heads; and
H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between instructional competencies and management behavior of the school heads.

FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

The theoretical and conceptual frameworks of the study are presented in light of the key concepts and variables in the due course of its proceedings.

Theoretical framework. This study is supported by various theories to strengthen the claims of the present study. It is commonly understood that most people do not want things to change. Instructional leaders, striving to improve student learning, must be involved in making changes - changes in behavior or practices and changes in beliefs and understanding. Therefore, it is helpful for the principal to understand the stages that change undergoes.

The Apartment Model of Change Theory as outlined by De Boer highlights four stages: 1. Contentment is what you feel before change is initiated. 2. Confusion is what you feel once the questions start to come. 3. Chaos is what you feel when answers come. 4. Self-renewal is what you feel when answers are settled.

Movement progresses in such a manner that we may be at different stages on different issues, all at one time. Havelock's (1973) stages of change are similar. However, he incorporates the role of the change agent that acts as catalyst, process helper, resource linker, or solution giver (Figure 2). Although all four change agent roles may be taken by the principal at some stage or other, the change agent as process helper is most useful for the supervisory role. It is a collaborative, on-going role. Following are Havelock's six stages of change. Stage I: Building a Relationship (between change agent & client) Stage II: Diagnosing the Problem Stage III: Acquiring Relevant Resources Stage IV: Choosing the Solution Stage V: Gaining Acceptance Stage VI: Stabilizing the Innovation and Generating Self-Renewal (p. 11) This approach promotes collaborative problem solving with the teaching staff to bring about determined, necessary change.

Conceptual framework. The purpose of this study was to determine the influence of instructional competencies of school heads on teacher's management behavior, in order to present the school heads with an understanding of the existing needs of the teachers. Based on what the needs are, the school heads would be encouraged to examine what changes may be needed in the school, so that instructional competencies could be more effectively incorporated into the school.

As illustrated, the dependent and independent variables served as the parameters outlined in the study. The socio-demographic profile of the respondents which include the school principals (gender, age, civil status, highest educational attainment and years of experience), the teachers (gender, age, civil status, highest educational attainment and number of years in teaching) and performance constitute the dependent variables; whereas, the instructional competencies and management behavior of the school heads are the independent variables.

The interplay of these variables is expected to create a school environment that would create opportunities for the school heads to improve their instructional competencies and for the teachers to learn and grow individually and professionally. The schematic diagram for the conceptual framework of the study is presented in figure 1.

Figure 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

The study employed the descriptive-correlational survey design using the survey questionnaire as the main instrument for generating the data.

The design fits the study since the numerical data collected at the outset were used to inform the collection of narrative data in the second stage of the study. The narrative data supported a more thorough understanding of the numerical data obtained in the first phase. Analysis of the numerical data provided a general understanding of research questions.

The study was conducted within the 5 areas of Leyte Division. These 5 areas included Tanauan II, Jaro, Javier, Tabango and Mahaplag.

A total of 200 respondents composed of 150 elementary teachers and 50 elementary school heads were tapped as respondents of the study. Each district was taken with twenty (20) percent of the total population.

A questionnaire was developed to collect data from the sampled school heads and teachers. This was pretested through a dry-run in other schools not included as respondents. The following sections provide a detailed description of the development and testing of this questionnaire. The questionnaire for the school heads has three parts: (a) questions gathering demographic information on the school heads which include gender, age, civil status, highest educational attainment and years of experience as school head; (b) instructional competencies of the school heads and (c) management behavior of the school heads. To validate the data from the school head-respondents, the same set of questionnaires were adopted but with slight modification on the teacher's socio-demographic profile was used to get responses from the teachers for triangulation of the results from both respondents.

Prior to conduct of the survey, the researcher first prepared sets of communications which asked permission from identified authorities to conduct the study. After the permission was obtained, the researcher personally administered the survey to selected and identified respondents. They were given one week to answer the questionnaires. To validate the data from selected respondents, the researcher also conducted unstructured interview to other chosen school heads and teachers outside the schools where the respondents were taken. Retrieval of the questionnaires was at ninety (90) percent.

Data were analyzed using the scoring reflected in the questionnaire. For the level of instructional competencies of the school heads, the scales below with corresponding descriptions/interpretations were observed:

Range	Descriptive Interpretation
1 -	Not Competent
2 -	Poorly Competent
3 -	Slightly Competent
4 -	Competent
5 -	Very Competent

In measuring the management behavior of the school heads, the scales with its descriptions/interpretations were reflected.

Range	Descriptive Interpretation
1 -	Ineffective
2 -	Minimally Effective

3	-	Satisfactorily Effective
4	-	Highly Effective
5	-	Outstandingly Effective

The data that were gathered in this study was subjected to statistical analysis using descriptive statistics such as mean, range, relative frequency and percentage.

Correlational analysis and t-test were also used to ascertain the significant relationships between variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-demographic Profile of the School Heads

Table 1 shows the socio-demographic profile of the school heads in terms of gender, age, civil status, highest educational attainment and years of experience as school head.

Table 1 Profile of the School Heads

Gender	f	Percentage
Male	10	20.00
Female	40	80.00
Total	50	100.00

Age	f	Percentage
23 – 30 years old	5	10.00
31 – 38 years old	5	10.00
39 – 46 years old	17	34.00
47 – 54 years old	20	40.00
55 – 62 years old	3	6.00
Total	50	100.00

Civil Status	f	Percentage
Single	8	16.00
Married	40	80.00
Widow/Widower/Separated	2	4.00
Total		100.00

Highest Educational Attainment	f	Percentage
BS Degree Holder	11	22.00
BS Degree with Masteral Units	19	38.00
Masters Degree with Doctoral Units	14	28.00
Doctorate Degree	6	12.00
Total	50	100.00

Years of Experience as a School Head	f	Percentage
Less than 5 years	8	17.02
5 – 9 years	11	23.40
10 – 14 years	6	12.77
15 – 19 years	9	19.15
20 – 24 years	8	17.02

More than 25 years	5	10.64
Total	47	100.00

Gender. Eighty-percent or 40 of the school heads were female and 10 or 20 percent were male. This indicates that female school heads outnumbered the male ones.

Age bracket. Almost one-half or 40 percent of the school heads were old, followed by the middle aged with a frequency of 17 or 34 percent. On the lowest were those on the senior category with a frequency of 3 or 6 percent. Most school heads are in the position for a long period of time.

Civil status. Majority of the school heads or 80 percent were married, eight or 16 percent were single and 2 or 4 percent were widow/widower/separated. This implies that a greater number of the school heads are family-oriented.

Highest educational attainment. Many of the respondents or 38 percent were BS degree holders with master's units, followed by those with master's degrees with doctoral units with a frequency of 14 or 28 percent and those with doctorate degrees were at the bottom with a frequency of 6 or 12 percent. The school heads could still upgrade their academic qualifications to increase the number of those having doctorate degrees.

Years of experience as school head. Eleven or 23.40 percent being the greater number of the school heads held the position for 5-9 years and the least number of the school heads were five or 10.64 percent who were in the position for more than 25 years.

Socio-demographic Profile of the Teachers

Table 2 shows the socio-demographic profile of the teachers in terms of gender, age, civil status, highest educational attainment and number of years in teaching.

Table 2 Profile of the Teachers

Gender	f	Percentage
Male	10	13.20
Female	66	86.80
Total	76	100.00

Age	f	Percentage
22 - 30 years old	9	12.00
31 – 39 years old	27	36.00
40 – 48 years old	22	29.33
49 – 56 years old	13	17.33
57 – 65 years old	4	5.34
Total	75	100.00

Civil Status	f	Percentage
Single	8	11.10
Married	63	87.50
Widow/Widower/Separated	1	1.40
Total		100.00

Highest Educational Attainment	f	Percentage
BS Degree Holder	21	29.17
BS Degree with Masteral Units	37	51.39
Masters Degree with Doctoral Units	10	13.89
Doctorate Degree	4	5.55
Total	72	100.00

Less than 5 years	10	14.29
5 – 9 years	18	25.71
10 – 14 years	10	14.29
15 – 19 years	11	15.71
20 – 24 years	17	24.29
More than 25 years	4	5.71
Total	70	100.00

Gender. Nearly 90 percent of the teachers with a frequency of 66 or 86.80 percent were female while the male were the least in number with a frequency of 10 or 13.20 percent. The female teachers dominate the male ones.

Age. Gaining the top spot were the teachers in the age range 31-39 years old with a frequency of 27 or 36 percent, followed by those in the age range 40-48 years old with a frequency of 22 or 29.33 percent and on the lowest rank were only four or 5.34 percent who belonged to the age range 57-65 years old. This denotes that many of the teachers are middle age.

Civil status. Nearly ninety-percent of the teachers with a frequency of 63 or 87.50 percent were married, followed by the singles with a frequency of 8 or 11.10 percent and the last was only on with a frequency of one or 1.40 percent. This connotes that many of the teachers are married and family-oriented.

Highest educational attainment. A greater bulk of the teachers with a frequency of 37 or 51.39 percent were BS degree holders with Master's units, followed by those with BS degrees with a frequency of 21 or 29.17 percent and at the bottom were those having Doctorate degrees with a frequency of 4 or 5.55 percent. This means that the teachers still need to upgrade their academic qualifications to increase the number of those holding doctorate degrees.

Number of years in teaching. Most of the teachers with a frequency of 18 or 25.71 percent were in the profession for 5-9 years, closely followed by those in the range 20-24 years with a frequency of 17 or 24.29 percent. Ranked last were only 4 or 5.71 percent who fell on the range more than 25 years.

Teacher Performance

The teacher's performance was determined through secondary data retrieved from the Department of Education Office in Leyte Division. This included data from SY 2012-2014. This is presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Teacher Performance

Year	Performance	Description
SY: 2013 – 2014	8.58	Very Satisfactory
SY: 2012 – 2013	8.56	Very Satisfactory
SY: 2011 - 2012	8.55	Very Satisfactory
Average	8.56	Very Satisfactory

As exhibited in the table, the teachers' performance for the period covered were very satisfactory which means that they performed their job very well.

Instructional Competency (as Rated by the School Heads)

The instructional competencies of the school heads contain ten indicators as reflected and measured in the table. This is presented in Table 4.

Table 4 Level of Instructional Competencies of the School Head

Indicators on Instructional Competency	WM	Description
School Head assists teachers in lesson planning.	4.04	Competent
SH assists teachers in developing/selecting instructional materials	3.95	Competent
SH helps teachers to evaluate curricula and suggest changes to meet the students' needs.	3.88	Competent
SH encourages teachers to use appropriate methods of teaching.	4.10	Competent
SH assists teachers in evaluating student performance.	3.95	Competent
SH advises teachers about new developments in teaching.	4.06	Competent
SH conducts meetings with teachers to review progress.	4.06	Competent
SH communicates with administrators about instructional concerns.	4.00	Competent
SH communicates with teachers about instructional concerns.	4.10	Competent
SH promotes the exchange of ideas and materials among teachers.	4.06	Competent
Average Weighted Mean	4.02	Competent

Instructional competencies. As reflected in the table, instructional competencies of the school heads generated an average weighted mean of 4.02 and rated as competent. All indicators fell on the same category interpreted as competent. It shows that the school heads are competent when it comes to instruction. Ideally, this would push for an implication that the school heads prioritize instruction and support the teachers in the advancement of any instructional goal and objective of the school.

Professional Competency (as Rated by the School Heads)

The professional competency of the school heads is measured by the following indicators and presented in Table 5.

Table 5 Professional Competency of the School Heads

Indicators on Professional Competency	WM	Description
SH directs all supervisory activities for the teachers' improvement.	4.14	Competent
SH helps to facilitate teachers' access to professional resources.	4.05	Competent
SH evaluates the performance of teachers.	4.23	Very Competent
SH uses evaluation as a means for development.	4.18	Competent
SH evaluates teachers only through their classroom performance.	4.02	Competent
SH uses more than one source in evaluating teachers.	4.02	Competent
SH provides feedback and offer suggestions for instructional improvement.	4.05	Competent
SH encourages teachers' professional growth.	4.19	Competent
SH conducts in-service programs to improve the performance of teachers.	3.87	Competent
SH conducts orientation activities for new teachers.	3.92	Competent
Average Weighted Mean	4.06	Competent

Professional competency. As indicated in the table, the professional competency of the school heads scored an average weighted mean of 4.06 labeled as competent. From the given indicators, only one on "SH evaluates the performance of teachers" was rated very competent with a weighted mean of 4.23. This suggests that the school heads are professionally competent and they are very skilled and adept particularly on evaluation of teacher performance. Further, it also implies that the school heads observes teacher performance evaluation regularly and properly.

Indicators on Motivation	WM	Description
SH is an example of good work and behavior for me to follow.	3.87	Competent
I consider the SH as a symbol and sign of success and accomplishment in our teaching profession.	3.92	Competent
SH inspires and encourages teachers to aim high in our teaching job and in life.	4.00	Competent

SH makes me feel proud to be associated with him/her.	3.99	Competent
SH has a special ability and talent for seeing what is really important formed to consider in my teaching job and life.	3.82	Competent
SH encourages me to hope for a bright future in our teaching profession and in life.	3.78	Competent
SH inspires loyalty and commitment to the department.	3.86	Competent
SH encourages me to express my ideas and opinions in staff meetings.	3.78	Competent
SH shows a sense of duty and work commitment which he/she transmits to me.	4.08	Competent
SH stimulates and encourages teachers to participate willingly and happily in doing departmental duties.	4.04	Competent
Average Weighted Mean	3.91	Competent

Motivation. As presented in the table, motivation obtained a frequency of 3.91 interpreted as competent. All the indicators were rated competent which shows that the school heads are competent enough in giving motivation to the teachers and staff. This would mean that motivation is given premium by the school heads as one of the cultural norm nurtured within the organization.

Instructional Competencies (as Rated by the Teachers)

The instructional competencies of the school heads contain ten indicators as reflected and measured in the table. This is presented in Table 2.

Indicators on Instructional Competency	WM	Description
School Head assists teachers in lesson planning.	3.94	Competent
SH assists teachers in developing/selecting instructional materials	3.96	Competent
SH helps teachers to evaluate curricula and suggest changes to meet the students' needs.	4.11	Competent
SH encourages teachers to use appropriate methods of teaching.	4.11	Competent
SH assists teachers in evaluating student performance.	4.11	Competent
SH advises teachers about new developments in teaching.	4.07	Competent
SH conducts meetings with teachers to review progress.	4.09	Competent
SH communicates with administrators about instructional concerns.	4.07	Competent
SH communicates with teachers about instructional concerns.	4.08	Competent
SH promotes the exchange of ideas and materials among teachers.	3.89	Competent
Average Weighted Mean	4.04	Competent

As rated by the teachers, the instructional competencies of the school heads were found to be competent at a frequency of 4.04. This proves that the school heads are proactive and dedicated to providing the best instruction in their respective schools. Further, the result also implies of the harmonious working relationships between the school heads and their teachers.

Indicators on Professional Competency	WM	Description
SH directs all supervisory activities for the teachers' improvement.	3.89	Competent
SH helps to facilitate teachers' access to professional resources.	3.97	Competent
SH evaluates the performance of teachers.	4.03	Competent
SH uses evaluation as a means for development.	3.95	Competent
SH evaluates teachers only through their classroom performance.	3.82	Competent
SH uses more than one source in evaluating teachers.	3.78	Competent
SH provides feedback and offer suggestions for instructional improvement.	3.98	Competent
SH encourages teachers' professional growth.	3.98	Competent
SH conducts in-service programs to improve the performance of teachers.	3.87	Competent
SH conducts orientation activities for new teachers.	3.83	Competent
Average Weighted Mean	3.91	Competent

As regards the school heads' professional competency, the teachers rated their school heads competent with a frequency of 3.91. From the teachers' perspective, they considered their school heads professionally competent. This finding implies that the school heads are very capable of their jobs and they perform their obligations competently.

Indicators on Motivation	WM	Description
SH is an example of good work and behavior for me to follow.	3.83	Competent
I consider the SH as a symbol and sign of success and accomplishment in our teaching profession.	3.79	Competent
SH inspires and encourages teachers to aim high in our teaching job and in life.	3.89	Competent
SH makes me feel proud to be associated with him/her.	3.72	Competent
SH has a special ability and talent for seeing what is really important formed to consider in my teaching job and life.	3.60	Competent
SH encourages me to hope for a bright future in our teaching profession and in life.	3.87	Competent
SH inspires loyalty and commitment to the department.	3.86	Competent
SH encourages me to express my ideas and opinions in staff meetings.	3.74	Competent
SH shows a sense of duty and work commitment which he/she transmits to me.	3.87	Competent
SH stimulates and encourages teachers to participate willingly and happily in doing departmental duties.	3.89	Competent
Average Weighted Mean	3.81	Competent

For motivation, the school heads were rated by their teachers competent with a frequency of 3.81. This tells that the school heads are competent enough in providing motivation to their teaching force. Likewise, this also implies that the school heads are very supportive and dedicated to assisting their teachers in attaining the educational goal and objective of the school.

Management Behavior of the School Heads

The management behavior of the school heads was measured through their management behavior, key processes and core components. This is presented in table 6.

Table 6 Management Behavior of the School Heads (as Rated by the School Heads)

Indicators on Management Behavior	WM	Description
Sets a personal example of what he/she expects of others.	4.04	Highly Effective
Talks about future trends that will influence how school work gets done.	3.86	Highly Effective
Seeks out challenging opportunities that test his/ her own skills and abilities.	3.92	Highly Effective
Develops cooperative relationships among the people he/she works with.	3.82	Highly Effective
Praises people for a job well done.	3.92	Highly Effective
Spends time and energy making certain that the people he/she works with adhere to the principles and standards that they have agreed on.	3.74	Highly Effective
Describes a compelling image of what our future could be like.	4.04	Highly Effective
Challenges people to try out new and innovative ways to do their work.	4.02	Highly Effective
Actively listens to diverse points of view.	3.70	Highly Effective
Makes it a point to let people know about his/her confidence in their abilities.	3.76	Highly Effective
Follows through on promises and commitments he/she makes.	3.70	Highly Effective
Appeals to others to share an exciting dream of the future.	3.74	Highly Effective
Searches outside the formal boundaries of his/her organization for innovative ways to improve what they do.	3.52	Highly Effective
Treats others with dignity and respect.	3.96	Highly Effective
Makes sure people are creatively rewarded for their contributions to success of projects.	3.76	Highly Effective
Asks for feedback on how his/her actions affect other people's performance.	3.76	Highly Effective
Shows how their long-term interests can be realized by enlisting in a common vision.	3.70	Highly Effective
Asks "What can we learn?" when things don't go as expected.	3.60	Highly Effective
Supports the decisions that people make on their own.	3.68	Highly Effective
Publicly recognizes people who exemplify commitment to shared values.	3.60	Highly Effective
Builds consensus around a common set of values for running the organization	3.62	Highly Effective
Paints the "big picture" of what the school aspires to accomplish.	3.54	Highly Effective
Makes certain that the organization set achievable goals, make concrete plans, and establish measurable milestones for the projects and programs that we work on.	3.72	Highly Effective
Gives people a great deal of freedom and choice in deciding how to do their work.	3.72	Highly Effective
Finds ways to celebrate accomplishments.	3.82	Highly Effective
Is clear about his/her philosophy of leadership.	3.68	Highly Effective

Speaks with genuine conviction about the higher meaning and purpose of his/her people's work.	3.74	Highly Effective
Experiments and takes risks, even when there is a chance of failure.	3.86	Highly Effective
Ensures that people grow in their jobs by learning new skills and developing themselves.	3.66	Highly Effective
Gives the members of the team lots of appreciation and support for their contributions.	3.68	Highly Effective
Average Weighted Mean	3.76	Highly Effective

As gleaned in table 4 on the management behavior, the school heads were rated with an average weighted mean of 3.76 interpreted as highly effective. All the indicators of this component fell on the same category as highly effective. The data suggests that, in terms of the school heads management behavior, they are very highly effective. From this findings, implication can be drawn that the school heads exhibit the right management behavior which means that they perform their management function very well.

Table 7 Management Behavior of School Head on Key Processes (As Rated by the School Heads)

Key Processes	WM	Description
Advocating	3.62	Highly Effective
Communicating	3.42	Satisfactorily Effective
Implementing	3.70	Highly Effective
Monitoring	3.82	Highly Effective
Planning	3.82	Highly Effective
Supporting	3.90	Highly Effective
Average Weighted Mean	3.71	Highly Effective

As projected in the table on key processes, the school heads were found to be highly effective in this aspect with an average weighted mean of 3.71. From the given indicators, it can be observed that only communicating was rated satisfactorily effective with a weighted mean of 3.42. This data shows that communicating is weaker than the rest of the indicators. As an implication, it tells that the school heads need to relate with their teachers to improve communication between them.

Table 8 Management Behavior of School Heads in Core Components (As Rated by the School Heads)

Indicators	WM	Description
Culture of learning and professional behavior	3.80	Highly Effective
High standards for student learning	3.56	Highly Effective
Performance accountability	3.80	Highly Effective
Quality instruction	3.70	Highly Effective
Rigorous curriculum	3.66	Highly Effective
Average Weighted Mean	3.70	Highly Effective

Provided in table 6 is the management behavior of school heads in core components. They posted an average weighted mean of 3.70 equivalent to highly effective. The rest of the indicators also belonged to the category of highly effective. From the results it can be inferred that the school heads are indeed highly effective in terms of core component behaviors. From these, it would certainly imply that the school heads performed their jobs properly and maintained quality in professional behavior, standard for student learning, instruction and curriculum.

Table 9 Management Behavior of the School Heads (as Rated by the Teachers)

Indicators	WM	Description
Sets a personal example of what he/she expects of others.	3.99	Highly Effective
Talks about future trends that will influence how school work gets done.	4.00	Highly Effective
Seeks out challenging opportunities that test his/ her own skills and abilities.	3.87	Highly Effective
Develops cooperative relationships among the people he/she works with.	4.04	Highly Effective
Praises people for a job well done.	4.13	Highly Effective
Spends time and energy making certain that the people he/she works with adhere to the principles and standards that they have agreed on.	4.03	Highly Effective
Describes a compelling image of what our future could be like.	4.01	Highly Effective
Challenges people to try out new and innovative ways to do their work.	3.93	Highly Effective
Actively listens to diverse points of view.	4.09	Highly Effective
Makes it a point to let people know about his/her confidence in their abilities.	4.00	Highly Effective
Follows through on promises and commitments he/she makes.	3.76	Highly Effective
Appeals to others to share an exciting dream of the future.	3.83	Highly Effective
Searches outside the formal boundaries of his/her organization for innovative ways to improve what they do.	3.48	Satisfactorily Effective
Treats others with dignity and respect.	4.15	Highly Effective
Makes sure people are creatively rewarded for their contributions to success of projects.	3.84	Highly Effective
Asks for feedback on how his/her actions affect other people's performance.	3.96	Highly Effective
Shows how their long-term interests can be realized by enlisting in a common vision.	3.75	Highly Effective
Asks "What can we learn?" when things don't go as expected.	3.75	Highly Effective
Supports the decisions that people make on their own.	3.88	Highly Effective
Publicly recognizes people who exemplify commitment to shared values.	3.95	Highly Effective
Builds consensus around a common set of values for running the organization	3.87	Highly Effective
Paints the "big picture" of what the school aspires to accomplish.	3.80	Highly Effective
Makes certain that the organization set achievable goals, make concrete plans, and establish measurable milestones for the projects and programs that we work on.	3.83	Highly Effective
Gives people a great deal of freedom and choice in deciding how to do their work.	3.92	Highly Effective

Finds ways to celebrate accomplishments.	3.93	Highly Effective
Is clear about his/her philosophy of leadership.	3.91	Highly Effective
Speaks with genuine conviction about the higher meaning and purpose of his/her people's work.	3.88	Highly Effective
Experiments and takes risks, even when there is a chance of failure.	3.72	Highly Effective
Ensures that people grow in their jobs by learning new skills and developing themselves.	3.73	Highly Effective
Gives the members of the team lots of appreciation and support for their contributions.	3.93	Highly Effective
Average Weighted Mean	3.90	Highly Effective

Shown in table 4 on the management behavior, the school heads were rated with an average weighted mean of 3.90 interpreted as highly effective. All the indicators of this component fell on the same category as highly effective. The data suggests that, in terms of the school heads management behavior, they are very highly effective. From this findings, implication can be drawn that the school heads exhibit the right management behavior which means that they perform their management function very well.

Table 10 Management Behavior of School Head on Key Processes (As Rated by the Teachers)

Indicators	WM	Description
Advocating	3.83	Highly Effective
Communicating	3.87	Highly Effective
Implementing	3.69	Highly Effective
Monitoring	3.65	Highly Effective
Planning	3.76	Highly Effective
Supporting	3.96	Highly Effective
Average Weighted Mean	3.79	Highly Effective

As depicted in the table on key processes, the school heads were found to be highly effective in this aspect with an average weighted mean of 3.79. All of the indicators under this aspect received descriptions of highly effective. This data shows that the school heads are highly effective in key processes of management behaviors such as in advocating, communicating, implementing, monitoring, planning and supporting. This paves the way to an implication that the school heads take their jobs properly and fully well.

Table 11 Management Behavior of School Heads in Core Components (As Rated by the Teachers)

Indicators	WM	Description
Culture of learning and professional behavior	3.88	Highly Effective
High standards for student learning	3.81	Highly Effective
Performance accountability	3.77	Highly Effective
Quality instruction	3.96	Highly Effective
Rigorous curriculum	3.73	Highly Effective
Average Weighted Mean	3.83	Highly Effective

Portrayed in table 11 is the management behavior of school heads in core components. They posted an average weighted mean of 3.83 equivalent to highly effective. The rest of the indicators also belonged to the category of highly effective. From the results it can be inferred that the school heads are indeed highly effective in terms of core component behaviors. From these, it would certainly imply that the school heads performed their jobs properly and maintained quality in professional behavior, standard for student learning, instruction and curriculum.

Relationship of Variables

The relationship of variables is another objective measured in the study. This was ascertained to determine whether there are or no relationships existed among these variables. This is presented in the succeeding tables.

Table 12 Relationship between the Profile of the School Heads and Instructional Competencies

VARIABLE	X ²	df	Asymp. Sig.	Decision
Gender	25.521	19	0.144	Ho Accepted
Civil Status	72.520	38	0.001	Ho Rejected
Highest Educational Attainment	88.088	57	0.005	Ho Accepted
VARIABLE	r-value	Sig.(2-tailed)	Decision	
Age	0.213	0.138	Ho Accepted	
Number of Years	0.527	0.000	Ho Rejected	

The data on table 12 presents the relationship between the profile of the school heads and their instructional competencies. For the profile variables on gender, civil status and highest educational attainment, only the civil status shows a significant relationship as correlated to instructional competencies. The computed value (72.520) was greater than asymp. Sig. of 0.001 with the df of 38 at alpha = .005. The hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the civil status of the school heads and their instructional competencies was rejected and therefore significant. Implication can be drawn that the school heads' civil status is directly related or affected their instructional competencies.

On the other hand, for the profile variables on age and number of years as school head, the number of years as school head shows significant relationship. The computed value for the number of years as a school head 0.000 was lesser at alpha = 0.05. The hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between number of years as school head and instructional competencies of the school heads was rejected and therefore significant. Findings draw implication that the number of years as a school head directly relates or affects the instructional competencies of the school heads.

Table 13 Relationship between the Profile of the School Heads and their Management Behavior

VARIABLE	X ²	df	Asymp. Sig.	Decision
Gender	21.354	26	0.723	Ho Accepted
Civil Status	50.838	52	0.520	Ho Accepted
Highest Educational Attainment	67.786	78	0.789	Ho Accepted
VARIABLE	r-value	Sig.(2-tailed)	Decision	
Age	0.099	0.493	Ho Accepted	
Number of Years	0.020	0.895	Ho Accepted	

Displayed in the table is the data between the profile of the school heads and their management behavior. For the profile variables on gender, civil status, highest educational attainment, age and number of years as correlated to management behavior, the computed values of these variables were greater than the r-values. The hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the profile and management behavior of the school heads was accepted and therefore not significant. The results imply that the profile does not relate or affect the management behavior of the school heads.

Table 14 Relationship between Instructional Competencies and Management Behavior of School Heads

VARIABLE	r-value	Sig.(2-tailed)	Decision
Instructional Competency	0.013	0.929	Ho Accepted

Highlighted in table 14 is the relationship between instructional competencies and management behavior of school heads. The computed r-value of 0.013 was lesser than the sig. value of 0.929. The hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between instructional competencies and management behavior of school heads was accepted and therefore not significant. Implication suggests that the instructional competencies do not relate to the management behavior of the school heads.

CONCLUSION

After thorough analysis of the results based from the findings based from the findings gathered from the study, the researcher came up with a number of conclusions.

On the profile, the civil status and number of years as school head were significantly related to the instructional competencies of the school heads.

As to instructional competencies, the school heads possessed the competence in performing their job related to their position.

In professional competency, the school heads were very competent in evaluating the performance of their teachers.

On the hindsight, the instructional competencies of the school heads did not relate or affect their management behavior.

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